

RESIDUAL STRESS MEASUREMENT OF CFRP BY X-RAY DIFFRACTION

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ABSTRACT

In this study, residual stresses in carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) were measured by the x-ray stress measurement technique. FRP always have the residual stresses because of the large difference of thermal expansion coefficient between the matrix phase and the fiber phase. Therefore, the residual stress estimation in FRP is very important. X-ray stress measurement is one of the non-distractive measurement method, and it was widely used to measure residual stresses with the so-called $\sin^2\psi$ method. However, this measurement is not many used in FRP because there are some problems for measuring residual stresses in polymer and carbon fibers. Firstly, the diffraction peaks from the polymer and/or the carbon fibers appear at the low 2θ angle region. Therefore, the measurement accuracy for strains reduces. Secondly, the low 2θ angle region is extremely difficult to use the $\sin^2\psi$ method. To resolve these problems, the transmission diffraction method with Ω -diffractometer method was employed in this study, though the x-ray stress measurement used the reflection method in usual case. From our investigation for three years, residual stresses in the polyamide matrix were able to estimate by x-ray stress measurement. The important parameters of the x-ray elastic constant in polyamide matrix and Poisson's ratio was investigated[1]. Furthermore, when the polyamide sample included the plastic deformation, the x-ray stress measurement was not available for polyamide sample. In this study, we try the next step to measure the residual stress in carbon fiber by x-ray stress measurement. From the FRP peak profile, each peaks of the polyamide matrix and the carbon fiber appear in different diffraction angles. Therefore, the residual stress in each material have the possibility to measure by the x-ray stress measurement.

1 INTRODUCTION

The fiber reinforced plastics always keeps residual stresses in the fiber phase and the matrix phase, because there is large different of thermal expansion coefficient between the fiber and the matrix [2,3]. For example, few reports is published in x-ray stress measurement of the polymer [4]. However, in many cases, residual stresses in polymer materials were calculated indirectly from the stress value of the metallic particle or the metal fiber phase in the composite [5]. It is better for it to be able to directly measure the stress in polymer matrix and the carbon fibers by the x-ray diffraction.

In this study, residual stresses in long carbon fiber phase of the composite material were measured by x-ray stress measurement. This measurement is widely used to measure residual stresses, and so-called $\sin^2\psi$ method is common non-destructive technique for evaluation residual stresses in near surface layer. On the other hand, an x-ray beam penetrate easy into the carbon fiber because there is the low absorption coefficient. Therefore, we used the transmission method of x-ray diffraction instead of the traditional reflection method.

2 BASIC THEORY OF X-RAY STRESS MEASUREMENT

Figure 1 shows the coordinate system of the x-ray stress measurement in this study. Regarding the theory of x-ray stress measurement, if the angle ψ is defined between the normal direction of the diffraction plane and the normal axis of the sample surface, the equation of the $d\text{-}\sin^2\psi$ method under the plane stress (uniaxial loading) condition can be expressed as:

Figure 1: Definition of coordinate system and ψ angle.

$$\sigma_x = \frac{E}{1+\nu} \cdot \frac{1}{d_0} \cdot \frac{\partial d_\psi}{\partial \sin^2\psi}, \quad (1)$$

where E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, d_0 is stress free lattice spacing, d_ψ is lattice spacing in the tilt angle ψ and direction of σ_x is coincided with the principle direction in uniaxial loading. The term $\partial d_\psi / \partial (\sin^2\psi)$ in Eq.(1) is calculated from the gradient of the regression line in the $d\text{-}\sin^2\psi$ diagram. Thus σ_x can be calculated from Eq.(1) with $d\text{-}\sin^2\psi$ diagram. $E/(1+\nu)$ is called the x-ray elastic constant (XEC) which can also be expressed by

$$\frac{1}{2}s_2 = \frac{1+\nu}{E} = \frac{1}{d_0} \cdot \frac{\partial M}{\partial \sigma}, \quad (2)$$

where M is $\partial d / \partial (\sin^2\psi)$. The XEC connects macroscopic stresses and the lattice strain calculated from the lattice spacing d_ψ .

The x-ray stress measurement employed the reflection method cannot use for the carbon fiber because the diffraction angle of carbon fibers appear only few angle regions and the tilt angles ψ were not kept the enough region for the stress measurement. In this study, we use the transmission method to resolve these problems. Fig.2 shows schematic diagrams of the x-ray stress measurement method; (a)reflection method, (b)transmission method. From Fig.2(a), when the sample was tilted, the diffraction profile from carbon fiber is disappeared in the reflection method because of the texture in the carbon fiber. On the other hand, in the case of transmission method, the diffraction profile from carbon fiber appears in every ψ angles.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of $d\text{-}\sin^2\psi$ method.

3 SAMPLE PREPARATION

In this study, the carbon fiber of T300-3000 produced by TORAY Co.,Ltd was used for the tensile testing sample. Table 1 shows the characteristics of T300-3000 and Fig.3 shows the appearance of the tensile testing sample. The sample is produced with based on Japanese Industrial Standard (JIS R 7606:2000). From the tensile testing, we could get the characteristics as well as values of TORAY Co.,Ltd informations. Fig.4 shows the result of stress-strain curves by the tensile testing of T300-3000. In Fig.4, the tensile testing was used for the INSTRON tensile testing machine. The tensile speed is 1mm/min in all cases. Characteristics of T300-3000 in Table 1 was measured by the tensile testing performed ourselves. On the other hand, the x-ray stress measurement will be need for a long time, because the diffraction peak from the carbon fiber has weak strength. In the long time measurement, the effect of creep deformation occurs in sometime. Therefore, it is very important to estimate the creep deformation for the accurate measurement. For the creep testing in this study, the testing sample of the carbon fiber were loaded 220N by the INSTRON tensile testing machine, and kept in the same displacement for 10 hours. The creep deformation was estimated from alterations of load values. Fig.5 shows the result of the creep testing for the carbon fiber. From this result, the large creep deformation occurred at first 10 minutes. The loaded value decreases 7% in first 10 minutes, and effect of the total creep deformation is 30% decrease after 10 hours. From these results, the loading value was explained the average load from start to end in this study.

Figure 3: The sample of carbon fiber for tensile testing.

Maximum stress [MPa]	3260
Maximum strain [%]	1.5
Young's modulus [GPa]	233
Value of fiber	3000
Density [g/cm ³]	1.76

Table 1: Characters of T300-3000

Figure 4: Results of tensile testing of carbon fiber.

Figure 5: Result of creep testing for 10 hours.

4 X-RAY STRESS MEASUREMENT

In this study, the small tensile system was mounted on the Ω -diffractometer. From the pre-experiment, the available region of the ψ angle in this study is from $\sin^2\psi=0.5$ to 1.0. The sample of the carbon fiber was measured by d - $\sin^2\psi$ method at several loads. Table 2 shows the condition of x-ray stress measurement. In this study, the tensile stresses were loaded by the screw device of the tensile testing system. The applied load was measured by the strain gages pasted on the chucking device. Fig.6(a) shows the small tensile system with strain gages and the loading screw. Fig.6(b) shows a photograph of one example of the transmission measurement method.

Characteristic x-rays	CuK α
X-ray optics	Parallel beam slits
Tube voltage	35kV
Tube Current	25mA
$\sin^2\psi$	0.5~1.0,0.1 step
hkl plane	unknown
Diffraction angle	$2\theta=43.44^\circ$
Filter	Nikkel
Irradiate area	5mm \times 2mm

Table 2: Condition of x-ray stress measurement.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6: Photograph of the small tensile testing system; (a) strain gages and the loading screw, (b) one example of transmission measurement method. The small tensile system mounted on a Ω -diffractometer.

5 Results and Discussion

Figure 7 shows the result of the polyamide in $\sin^2\psi$ method. This results were cited from the other paper of the same author[1]. Fig.8 shows the result of the carbon fiber in this study. From these results, in the case of the polyamide, there were good linearly and the gradients of regression lines is increasing with applied loads rising. On the other hand, in the case of the carbon fiber, the linearity of regression lines was not very good. Furthermore, there was the large positive gradient in the stress free condition: 0N. In the case of polyamide in Fig.7, the regression line in the stress free state is almost no gradient, it like a horizontal line. Fig.9 shows peak profiles from the carbon fiber. From this figure, the

shape of the diffraction profile from the carbon fiber changed broadly with the ψ angle change from $\sin^2\psi=1.0$ to 0.5. Furthermore, the peak profile in the left side were not change. However, the right side were much shift and broad. Therefore, in the case of carbon fiber, the existence of the large positive gradient of d - $\sin^2\psi$ diagram in the stress free state was generated from these broadening in the right side of peak profiles.

Figure:7 d - $\sin^2\psi$ diagram of polyamide.

(T. Doi, M. Nishida, J. Ozaki. Residual Stress Measurement of Industrial Polymers by X-ray Diffraction, Advanced Material Research, Vol.1110, 2015, pp100-103.)

Figure 8: d - $\sin^2\psi$ diagram of carbon fibers.

Figure 9: Peak profiles from the carbon fiber.

Figure 10 shows the $\partial d/\partial(\sin^2\psi)$ vs. σ diagram of polyamide cited results[1], and Fig.11 shows the $\partial d/\partial(\sin^2\psi)$ vs. σ diagram of carbon fiber in this study. From results of the polyamide, gradients of the polyamide increase from 0.02 to 0.15 with applied stresses rising. On the other hand, in the case of the carbon fiber, gradients also increase with the applied stresses rising. Alterations of the gradient is from 0.08 to 0.092. Though these are very small change of gradients in the carbon fiber, we are considering that it is possible to estimate the x-ray elastic constant (XEC) from these results if we try to measure with care and precision. We need to resolve these problems in near future.

Figure 10: Relationship between $\partial d/\partial(\sin^2\psi)$ and applied stresses.
(T. Doi, M. Nishida, J. Ozaki. Residual Stress Measurement of Industrial Polymers by X-ray Diffraction, Advanced Material Research, Vol.1110, 2015, pp100-103.)

Figure 11: The relationship between $\partial d/\partial(\sin^2\psi)$ and Applied stresses.

6 CONCLUSION

1. When the carbon fiber is measured by x-ray stress measurement with transmission method, the peak profiles shift for high angle side with the ψ angle change from to $\sin^2\psi=1.0$ to 0.5. Therefore, the regression line in d - $\sin^2\psi$ diagram has the large positive gradient in the stress free state.
2. For the x-ray stress measurement of the carbon fiber, the alteration of lattice space d is very small with applied stresses rising. However, these is possibility to measure the stresses with care and accuracy measurement.

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